

Gender Quotas, Women's Leadership, and Grassroots Women Activists: Bringing Women into the Party in Nepal

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Abstract

The growing issue of women's participation in national-level governing bodies and national-level policy formation in Nepal remains a subject of ongoing debate and discussion, attracting increasing attention and scrutiny from various stakeholders and advocates for gender equality and women's rights. Previous studies have highlighted the growing issue of women's participation in Nepal's national-level governing bodies and policy formation, which underline the ongoing debate and discussion surrounding this topic, emphasising the increasing attention and scrutiny from stakeholders and advocates for gender equality and women's rights. Our study examines these women's opinions, experiences, and parliamentary roles in governing executive positions and participating in national-level policies.

Our study applied a quantitative approach connecting with cognitivism to understand the opinions and experiences of women politicians on their roles to empower women in Nepal. The quantitative methodology enables a nuanced understanding of the changing gender dynamics and its implications for Nepal's political landscape, providing valuable insights for policymakers, scholars, and advocates alike. Through the survey study aims to capture the nuanced experiences, perceptions, and challenges women politicians face. The descriptive analysis has been applied to analyse the survey data.

The analysis of quantitative data would reveal nuanced insights into the transformative impact of women in Nepali politics to empower them. It would highlight their empowerment, the evolving gender dynamics, and the influential role of female leaders in shaping central and provincial-level policies. These findings underscore the significance of increased female representation in reshaping Nepal's political landscape. Our research sheds light on the transformative effects of increased female representation in Nepali politics by exploring women's critical roles, contributions, and impact on policymaking at the central and provincial levels.

Keywords: *advocates for gender equality, gender disparity, Nepal's political landscape, policy formation, women's participation*